

Energy and Flexibility Modelling

Hands-on 3 (macOS)

Please use the following citation for:

- **This exercise**

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- **clicSANDMac Software**

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- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

Please sign up to the help Google forum [here](#). If you are stuck, please ask questions here. If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'clicSAND' Interface.

Learning outcomes

By the end of this exercise, you will be able to:

1. Draw a RES with a Backstop and a demand
2. Define fuels
3. Define energy demands for a specific fuel
4. Define the temporal profile of energy demands
5. Define a simple technology that satisfies the demand (Backstop)
6. Run the model and check results

Draw RES with a Backstop and a demand

The first thing you will learn in this exercise is to draw a Reference Energy System (RES). As explained in Lecture 2, a RES is a conventional aggregated representation of a real energy system.

Different tools are available for this purpose, but they vary in price and functionality. For this course, we will choose [Diagram.net](https://diagrams.net) which is a **free** software to draw diagrams.

1. Open [Diagram.net](https://diagrams.net) in your browser and click **Start**.

Blog

Start Now

Security-first diagramming for teams.

Bring your storage to our online tool, or go max privacy with the desktop app.

No login or registration required.

2. Click **Create New Diagram**

Change storage

3. Change the Filename to "**HandsOn3.drawio**" and select '**Blank Diagram**'. Click on '**Create**' and save it in a folder of preference. **Tip:** create a folder for each Hands-On exercise of this course and keep building your RES, adding every piece proposed in the exercises.

4. On the left side of the tool, select a Rectangle from the General Group. Drag and drop it on the screen.
5. Double click in the middle of the **Rectangle** to add Text. Write **BACKSTOP**.

- Let's draw the electricity demand. Select a **line** and drag and drop it on the right side of the Backstop technology. Bring your pointer on the right side of the rectangle and some **blue points** will appear. Click and drag until you reach the demand line, drawing an **arrow**. Double click on top of the demand line to add the code for the electricity demand: **ELC003** as per the **naming convention** guidelines explained in **Lecture 3**.

You have now drawn the first technology called **Backstop** and the final electricity demand (**ELC003**). The arrow that connects the two means that the output of the Backstop technology will address the final electricity demand (**ELC003**).

Define commodities

The next step is to add the names of our fuels in SAND Interface.

1. In the HO2 folder, make a copy of "**SAND_Interface_HO2**".
2. **Rename it as "SAND_Interface_HO3" and move it to a new HO3 folder** (by copying this file in the new Hands-On folder we will avoid having to re-add the data already saved in Hands-On 2). Therefore, after Hands-On 2, you will not use the SAND Interface template created by clicSAND, but you will keep adding data to what you have previously done.

IMPORTANT: make copies when you move to the next HO and do not make edits on the same file. In this way if there is a problem, there is always a back-up version to easily find the error.

3. Go to the **SETS** Sheet. Click on Cell E3 and change the code from "**COM001**" to "**ELC003**".
4. Add a description in Cell F3 changing the text from "**Additional Fuel**" to "**Electricity after distribution**".

Commodities	
Code	Description
ELC003	Electricity after distribution
COM002	Additional Fuel
COM003	Additional Fuel
COM004	Additional Fuel
COM005	Additional Fuel

Tip: Repeat this process in the future to add names for other Commodities (Fuels).

Define energy demands for a specific fuel

Your next task will be to choose the demand type. You have two options for demand type:

- **SpecifiedAnnualDemand** – used for fuels whose demand varies within the year/day e.g. electricity
- **AccumulatedAnnualDemand** – used for fuels that do not necessarily have to be provided at an exact point in time e.g. gasoline

We will add the demand for Electricity after distribution (**ELC003**).

1. Go to Parameters Sheet in SAND and filter out **SpecifiedAnnualDemand**.
2. Go on Cell K41971, correspondent to ELC003 (Fuel Column F).
3. Copy-paste the ELC003 demand data for the years 2015-2070. You can find the data in this [Data_prep file](#) (copy-paste only the data from the 'Specified Annual Demand' sheet, column J to column BN).

	A	F	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
1	Parameter	FUEL	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
41971	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	ELC003	28.5228	29.7936	32.166	34.5385	36.9109	39.28334	41.4087	43.68493	46.12041	48.72429
41972	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41973	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41974	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41975	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41976	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41977	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41978	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41979	SpecifiedAnnualDemand	COM009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Tip: For the same Commodity (Fuel) you should never add data for both **SpecifiedAnnualDemand** and **AccumulatedAnnualDemand**. Choose the type of demand associated with that fuel following the indications given in **Lecture 4**.

You now know how to add a **SpecifiedAnnualDemand**!

Define the temporal profile of energy demands

SpecifiedAnnualDemand is the parameter used to define a demand that changes within the year, as per the final electricity demand just seen (ELC003). Therefore, it is now important to represent this time variability, and to do so we will use the **SpecifiedDemandProfile** parameter (as explained in Lecture 3).

If interested to know how the SpecifiedDemandProfile was calculated read this box

We divide the year into four representative seasons (Winter, Spring, Summer, and Autumn), further specifying the day-type (Day and Night for each of the four seasons). These eight representative day types are considered to have an equal length.

Therefore, the Year Split values for just 8 time slices are equal to $\frac{1}{8}$ (0.125) for each timeslice and reported on the left side of the table below. The 8 numbers are then modified to obtain the Year Split values for all the 96 timeslices available in SAND.

Year Split			Specified demand profile for electricity	
TimeSlice	value		TimeSlice	ELC003
Winter Day	0.125		Winter Day	0.136
Winter Night	0.125		Winter Night	0.110
Spring Day	0.125		Spring Day	0.136
Spring Night	0.125		Spring Night	0.109
Summer Day	0.125		Summer Day	0.14
Summer Night	0.125		Summer Night	0.111
Autumn Day	0.125		Autumn Day	0.144
Autumn Night	0.125		Autumn Night	0.115

Following the same procedure, we now need to understand how the data for the **SpecifiedDemandProfile** was calculated for 8 timeslices and how to manipulate them to obtain a 96 time slices representation in SAND.

The data reported on the right side of the table were obtained from free hourly demand dataset called PLEXOS.

From these data we can see that the demand is higher during the Days and lower during Nights. Therefore, by using our data preparation spreadsheet we will calculate the percentage of average demand in each Time slice using the following formula:

$$[\text{Specified demand profile (SD)} / \text{Year split (SD)}] * \text{Bennett Factor} =$$

$$= [0.14/0.125] * 0.999 = 112\%$$

Data Manipulation			
Making adjustments for CCG SAND			
We'll assume equal season lengths (3 months each) and an average hourly split per season (24h)			
S1 will be winter, S2 will be spring, S3 will be summer, S4 will be autumn			
50%	or	12.0	hrs are in a summer night
50%	or	12.0	hrs are in a winter night
50%	or	12.0	hrs are in winter day
50%	or	12.0	hrs are in summer day
% of average demand in each timeslice			
	Winter Day	109%	
	Winter Night	88%	
	Spring Day	109%	
	Spring Night	87%	
	Summer Day	112%	
	Summer Night	89%	
	Autumn Day	115%	

Now we need to pass from 8 time slices to 96 in SAND. To do so, you need to multiply the average percentage of demand in each timeslice for the year split duration of that time slice.

To give you an example:

		% of average demand in each timeslice		
21				
22		Winter Day	109%	
23		Winter Night	88%	
24		Spring Day	109%	
25		Spring Night	87%	
26		Summer Day	112%	
27		Summer Night	89%	
28		Autumn Day	115%	
29		Autumn Night	92%	
30				
31		Bennett Factor		0.999
32		Sum	1.0000	1.0000
33			Year Split	Specified Demand Profile
34	Winter Night	S101	0.0104	=C34*\$C\$23
35	Winter Night	S102	0.0104	0.0092

You will find the SpecifiedDemandProfile in the [Data Preparation File](#) (for all the 96 timeslices that we are using in SAND).

Let's add the demand profile to SAND.

1. Go to Parameters Sheet and filter out for SpecifiedDemandProfile parameter.
2. Go to Column F of the fuels and filter out for ELC003.
3. Go to Cell K42021 and copy-paste the data for the specified demand profile from the [Data Preparation File](#) (the data you need is in Cell D34 to D129)
4. Drag and drop until year 2070.
5. Save.

	A	F	G	K	L	M
1	Parameter	FUEL	TIMESLICE	2015	2016	2017
42021	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S101	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42022	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S102	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42023	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S103	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42024	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S104	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42025	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S105	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42026	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S106	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42027	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S107	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42028	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S108	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42029	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S109	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42030	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S110	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42031	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S111	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42032	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S112	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42033	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S113	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42034	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S114	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42035	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S115	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42036	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S116	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42037	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S117	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42038	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S118	0.01132	0.01132	0.01132
42039	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S119	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42040	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S120	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42041	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S121	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42042	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S122	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42043	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S123	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42044	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S124	0.00919	0.00919	0.00919
42045	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S201	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42046	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S202	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42047	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S203	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42048	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S204	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42049	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S205	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42050	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S206	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42051	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S207	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42052	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S208	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42053	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S209	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42054	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S210	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42055	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S211	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42056	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S212	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42057	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S213	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42058	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S214	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42059	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S215	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42060	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S216	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42061	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S217	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42062	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S218	0.0113	0.0113	0.0113
42063	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S219	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42064	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S220	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42065	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S221	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42066	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S222	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42067	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S223	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42068	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S224	0.00905	0.00905	0.00905
42069	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S301	0.00925	0.00925	0.00925
42070	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S302	0.00925	0.00925	0.00925
42071	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S303	0.00925	0.00925	0.00925
42072	SpecifiedDemandProfile	ELC003	S304	0.00925	0.00925	0.00925

Tip: the sum of all the Year Split values for the 96 time slices should always be 1. The same is true for the SpecifiedDemandProfile values.

Define a simple technology that satisfies the demand (Backstop)

As explained in Lecture 4, Backstop technologies are a last resort option for the optimization solver, being fictitious technologies with extremely high cost. We will add a backstop technology with an output of electricity (ELC003) demand. Therefore, the backstop will be the only technology in the model able to supply the ELC003 demand we have added. To add the backstop, we need to add the data available here in the right place.

Try it: Add backstop technology

1. Go to Parameters Sheet and clear all the filters in case you didn't yet.
2. Go to SETS and in Cell B3 change "**TEC000**" to "**BACKSTOP**", and "**Additional Technology**" to "**Backstop Technology**".

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1		Technologies			Commodities	
2		<i>Code</i>	<i>Description</i>		<i>Code</i>	<i>Description</i>
3		BACKSTOP	Backstop Technology		ELC003	Electricity after distribution
4		TEC001	Additional Technology		COM002	Additional Fuel
		TEC002	Additional Technology		COM003	Additional Fuel

3. Go to the Parameters Sheet and filter out in Column C (Technology) for 'BACKSTOP'. You will now see all the parameters associated only to this technology.
4. You will need to add data in SAND as presented in the BACKSTOP Sheet of [the data preparation file](#). Remember to copy-paste the values until 2070.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
143	CapacityFactor	RE1	BACKSTOP				S424			1		1
144	CapacityOfOneT	RE1	BACKSTOP							0		0
145	CapacityToActiv	RE1	BACKSTOP						1			
146	CapitalCost	RE1	BACKSTOP							9999999	9999999	999
147	EmissionActivity	RE1	BACKSTOP	EMICO2		1				0		0
148	EmissionActivity	RE1	BACKSTOP	EMIO02		1				0		0
149	EmissionActivity	RE1	BACKSTOP	EMIO03		1				0		0
150	EmissionActivity	RE1	BACKSTOP	EMIO04		1				0		0
151	EmissionActivity	RE1	BACKSTOP	EMIO05		1				0		0
152	FixedCost	RE1	BACKSTOP							9999999	9999999	999
153	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	ELC003			0		0
154	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM002			0		0
155	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM003			0		0
156	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM004			0		0
157	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM005			0		0
158	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM006			0		0
159	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM007			0		0
160	InputActivityRat	RE1	BACKSTOP			1	COM008			0		0

5. Save your Excel file.

Tip: check cells highlighted in blue and be sure that the correspondent cell in SAND has that number! Make use of as many filters as needed for the input data process.

Run the model and check results on production by technology

It's time to run our first model.

1. Go to the 'SETS' sheet. Paste the path of the folder you'd like your results to be saved in. This could be the HO3 folder.

Emissions	
Code	Description
EMICO2	Emission factor for CO2
EMICH4	Emission factor for methane
EMIFGA	Emission factor for Fluorinated gases
EMIN2O	Emission factor for Nitrous Oxide
EMIREN	Emission factor for RET targets
Region	
RE1	Region 1
ResultsPath "C:\..\res\csv" (change it before running)	
=" /Users/naomitan/Desktop/CCG/Training/2a OSeMOSYS/Hands-On/HO3";	

2. Go to the 'ToDataFile' sheet on the SAND interface.
3. Click on the top left corner of the spreadsheet. This will select all the data within the sheet. Alternatively, you can press on the **command key (⌘) + A**.
4. Once highlighted, right click – copy. Alternatively, you can press on the **command key (⌘) + C**.
5. Now go to your 'Applications' folder and open an app called TextEdit. You will already have this app by default.

6. Click on 'New Document'.

- Once in TextEdit, right click – paste your data from the SAND interface. Alternatively, you can press on the **command key** (⌘) + V.

```
#####  
# Sets #  
#####  
#  
set EMISSION := EMIC02 EMICH4 EMIFGA EMIN20 EMIREN ;  
set REGION := RE1 ;  
set MODE_OF_OPERATION := 1 ;  
set FUEL := ELC003 COM002 COM003 COM004 COM005 COM006 COM007 COM008 COM009  
COM010 COM011 COM012 COM013 COM014 COM015 COM016 COM017 COM018 COM019 COM020 COM021  
COM022 COM023 COM024 COM025 COM026 COM027 COM028 COM029 COM030 COM031 COM032 COM033  
COM034 COM035 COM036 COM037 COM038 COM039 COM040 COM041 COM042 COM043 COM044 COM045  
COM046 COM047 COM048 COM049 COM050 ;  
set STORAGE := ;  
set TECHNOLOGY := BACKSTOP TEC001 TEC002 TEC003 TEC004 TEC005 TEC006 TEC007  
TEC008 TEC009 TEC010 TEC011 TEC012 TEC013 TEC014 TEC015 TEC016 TEC017 TEC018 TEC019  
TEC020 TEC021 TEC022 TEC023 TEC024 TEC025 TEC026 TEC027 TEC028 TEC029 TEC030 TEC031  
TEC032 TEC033 TEC034 TEC035 TEC036 TEC037 TEC038 TEC039 TEC040 TEC041 TEC042 TEC043  
TEC044 TEC045 TEC046 TEC047 TEC048 TEC049 TEC050 TEC051 TEC052 TEC053 TEC054 TEC055  
TEC056 TEC057 TEC058 TEC059 TEC060 TEC061 TEC062 TEC063 TEC064 TEC065 TEC066 TEC067  
TEC068 TEC069 TEC070 TEC071 TEC072 TEC073 TEC074 TEC075 TEC076 TEC077 TEC078 TEC079  
TEC080 TEC081 TEC082 TEC083 TEC084 TEC085 TEC086 TEC087 TEC088 TEC089 TEC090 TEC091  
TEC092 TEC093 TEC094 TEC095 TEC096 TEC097 TEC098 TEC099 TEC100 TEC101 TEC102 TEC103  
TEC104 TEC105 TEC106 TEC107 TEC108 TEC109 TEC110 TEC111 TEC112 TEC113 TEC114 TEC115  
TEC116 TEC117 TEC118 TEC119 TEC120 TEC121 TEC122 TEC123 TEC124 TEC125 TEC126 TEC127  
TEC128 TEC129 TEC130 TEC131 TEC132 TEC133 TEC134 TEC135 TEC136 TEC137 TEC138 TEC139  
TEC140 TEC141 TEC142 TEC143 TEC144 TEC145 TEC146 TEC147 TEC148 TEC149 TEC150 TEC151  
TEC152 TEC153 TEC154 TEC155 TEC156 TEC157 TEC158 TEC159 TEC160 TEC161 TEC162 TEC163  
TEC164 TEC165 TEC166 TEC167 TEC168 TEC169 TEC170 TEC171 TEC172 TEC173 TEC174 TEC175  
TEC176 TEC177 TEC178 TEC179 TEC180 TEC181 TEC182 TEC183 TEC184 TEC185 TEC186 TEC187  
TEC188 TEC189 TEC190 TEC191 TEC192 TEC193 TEC194 TEC195 TEC196 TEC197 TEC198 ;
```

- Save your new TextEdit file with a sensible name (i.e. **HO3_data**) in your new HO3 folder and close it. We now have a .txt file.
- Now go to your 'Applications' folder and open clicSANDMac

10. The screen below will show up. The button highlighted in red allows you to select the data txt file you want to run. **In this case**, we want to choose **HO3_data.txt**. The button highlighted in green allows you to select the model txt file. **In all cases**, we must choose **OSeMOSYS_code.txt**. You can obtain this coded txt file by clicking on 'Export Templates ...' – as explained in Hands-On 2.

11. When you have selected these two files, click on RUN. This is the button highlighted in yellow. **TIP:** Close any high memory (or disk) consuming programs for a faster run.

12. Now wait.... The solvers (glpsol and cbc) will run the txt file with the OSeMOSYS code to find the optimal solution.

13. You will see this on clicSANDMac if the run is successful.

14. You will now see three new files in your HO3 folder.

Results Visualization

We will now visualize the results from the model run.

1. Go to this [link](#) to download conversion.app.zip and Results_Visualization_Template.xlsx

The screenshot shows a file sharing interface with a list of files and a versions panel. The files list includes:

Name	Size	Preview	Download
Additional Info.zip	11.5 MB		
md5:48bdfeee01eb139a9feec5b4b027d614			
clicSANDMac.zip	13.7 MB		
md5:7a018fa12ebe5deba185caf9263cdf2e			
conversion.app.zip	49.2 MB		
md5:3371191b75b564c7c7242af8d21f1315			
Results_Visualization_Template.xlsx	8.9 MB		
md5:2b234a08090140bbc2143c6ea12bea86			

The versions panel on the right shows:

- Version v.1.1.0 (Jan 31, 2022)
- Version v.1.0.3 (Jan 20, 2022)
- Version v.1.0.2 (Jan 19, 2022)

Below the versions panel is a 'Share' button.

2. Once downloaded, unzip and right-click to open the conversion.app.zip file. This file will convert our results txt file to a csv file.

3. Click on 'Open'.

4. A window will pop-up. Click on 'Input file' and choose 'HO3_data.txt.results.txt'. For 'Output directory', choose your HO3 folder. Now choose an output name. In this case, we can write "HO3_results". Now click on 'Save output filename'.

- Click on 'Run' to finish. You will have a csv file in your HO3 folder called **"HO3_results.csv"**. Open this file. This will open a spreadsheet.

- Click on Cell A2. Now press on the **command key (⌘) + shift + right arrow + right arrow + down arrow**. This will select all the data in Columns A to L, without the header row.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Variable	Dim1	Dim2	Dim3	Dim4	Dim5	Dim6	Dim7	Dim8	Dim9	Dim10	ResultValue
2	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2015								32.825383
3	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2016								1.4625206
4	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2017								2.7303177
5	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2018								2.7303062
6	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2019								2.7303177
7	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2020								2.7303062
8	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2021								2.4459777
9	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2022								2.6195831
10	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2023								2.8028672
11	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2024								2.99667
12	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2025								3.2018202
13	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2026								4.1304394
14	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2027								4.414998
15	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2028								4.7184076
16	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2029								5.0417729
17	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP	2030								5.3864978

- Copy the data by pressing **command key (⌘) + C**.
- Now open the newly downloaded Results_Visualization_Template.xlsx file.

9. In the top ribbon, click on 'Enable Content'.

10. Click on Cell A2 and press on the **command key (⌘) + shift + right arrow + right arrow + down arrow** to highlight all the data in Columns A to L, without the header row. Now click on the delete key to delete the values.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Variable	Dir	Dim2	Dim3	Dim4	Dir	Dir	Dim7	Dir	Dir	Dim	ResultValue
2	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2018							750.43416
3	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2019							750.43416
4	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2020							750.43416
5	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2021							725.41968
6	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2022							700.40521
7	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2023							675.39074
8	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2024							650.37627
9	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2025							625.3618
10	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2026							625.3618
11	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2027							625.3618
12	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2028							625.3618
13	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2029							625.3618
14	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2030							625.3618
15	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2031							625.3618
16	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2032							625.3618
17	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2033							625.3618
18	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2034							587.364
19	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2035							625.3618
20	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2036							625.3618
21	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2037							625.3618
22	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2038							625.3618
23	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2039							625.3618
24	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2040							600.34732
25	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2041							540.31259
26	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2042							531.74199
27	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2043							560.32417
28	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2044							480.27786
29	NewCapacity	RE1	MINOIL		2045							300.17366

11. In a now empty Cell A2, paste the data with the **command key (⌘) + V**.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Variable	Dir	Dim2	Dim3	Dim4	Dir	Dir	Dim7	Dir	Dir	Dim	ResultValue
2	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2015							32.825383
3	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2016							1.4625206
4	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2017							2.7303177
5	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2018							2.7303062
6	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2019							2.7303177
7	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2020							2.7303062
8	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2021							2.4459777
9	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2022							2.6195831
10	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2023							2.8028672
11	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2024							2.99667
12	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2025							3.2018202
13	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2026							4.1304394
14	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2027							4.414998
15	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2028							4.7184076
16	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2029							5.0417729
17	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2030							5.3864978
18	NewCapacity	RE1	BACKSTOP		2031							5.9418971

12. We will first visualize Annual Electricity Production. Go to the 'AnnualElecProduction' Sheet. Click on Cell A3. 'PivotTable Analyze' should show up in the ribbon. Click on this, then click on 'Refresh'.

The screenshot shows a PivotTable with the following structure:

	A	B
1	Variable	(Multiple Items)
2		
3	Sum of ResultValue	Column Labels
4	Row Labels	Grand Total
5	Grand Total	

The PivotTable Analyze ribbon is visible, with the 'Refresh' button circled in red. The ribbon includes options like 'Options', 'Field Settings', 'Expand Field', 'Collapse Field', 'Group Selection', 'Insert Slicer', 'Insert Timeline', 'Filter Connections', and 'Change source'.

13. Now go to the filter setting of 'Column Labels' in Cell B3 and tick 'Select All'.

The screenshot shows the PivotTable with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Variable	ProductionByTechnologyAnnual				
2						
3	Sum of ResultValue	Column Labels				
4	Row Labels	BACKSTOP				
5	2015		28.522751			
6	2016		29.79357			
7	2017		27.16696			
8	2018					
9	2019					
10	2020					
11	2021					
12	2022					
13	2023					
14	2024					
15	2025					
16	2026					
17	2027					
18	2028					
19	2029					
20	2030					
21	2031					
22	2032					
23	2033					
24	2034					
25	2035					
26	2036					
27	2037					
28	2038					
29	2039					

The filter menu for 'Column Labels' is open, showing the following options:

- Sort: Ascending, Descending
- Sort by: Dim2
- Filter:
 - By label: Choose One
 - By value: Choose One
 - Search: [Search box]
 - Select All
 - DEMCOMELC
 - DEMINDEL
 - DEMRESEL
 - EMIC02
 - MINBIO
 - MINCOA

14. You will be able to see a table and a graph. Your results for Annual Electricity Production from this exercise are now visualized! Save the file as **results_visualization_HO3.xlsx**

In this graph, you will see that the only technology producing electricity is the BACKSTOP. This is because it is the only technology that we added in our energy system to provide ELC003.

15. You will also notice that this file is made of different Sheets for each of the variable we want to obtain results for:

Annual Electricity Production	Electricity Production by Timeslice	Annual Total Capacity	Cooking & Heat
Transport	Annual CO2	Annual CO2 by Technology	Demand
Annual Fixed Operating Costs	Annual Variable Operating Costs	Capital Investment	

The steps are the same for the above graphs.